

UBD SCHOOL OF BUSINESS

AND ECONOMICS

Design and Cultural Industries

Faculty of Arts & Social Sciences

Semester 3 – 2020/2021

Level 2000 Module

BB – 2208 Human Resource Management

Individual Assignment 2 – Case Study Analysis

Title: Syarikat Al Rasyid

Registration Number: 19b0131

Class: Thursday (1410-1500)

Date: 30th September 2020

1. Abstract

Syarikat Al Rasyid is an agricultural company specialized in paddy production. The owner, Muhammad Abdul Rasyid, became a certified rice paddy farmer in 2015 and started registering his company with interest in 2016 when the “Kursus Belia Berpadi” was completed in 2015. He has faced difficulties throughout the operation of the company, the majority of challenges he faces are land suitability and irrigation problems. He experiences challenges during the operation of the business, majority challenges he faced are the land suitability and irrigation issues (Musa et al 2020). Trying to incorporate the Warwick Model - system centered on improving success and market development through achieving an acceptable balance between internal and external contexts. The Warwick Model is used in his company to ensure that his business is doing well. This report paper would address the context and issue faced by Syarikat Al Rasyid as well as the implementation of the Warwick Model.

2. Introduction

Syarikat Al Rasyid is owned and administered by Muhammad Abdul Rasyid Bin Kamarudjaman, a paddy farmer with no family history on prior to any previous experience in agriculture. It is an agricultural business that specializes in paddy production. Started in 2015 but was registered on 4th October 2016. With little experience or expertise of agriculture, Rasyid is determined to learn more from the courage to delve into agriculture. He became a licensed rice paddy farmer in 2015, taught both theory and experience at the Paddy Unit of the Department of Agriculture, and even participated in some of the courses offered by the Rice Farmers Field School. In 2017, he and his peers were also selected to take part in a training programme to provide them with the expertise required to run and sustain the technologies used in farming. As mentioned above, Abdul Rasyid had no family background or previous farming experience since his father was a lecturer and his mother was a tailor. Therefore, he was seeking for mentors to train with. These advisors were expert farmers to provide instruction for him in the running of his farm. His commitment to contribute to the growth of the country is also very strong. As a

person who received the “Usahawan Belia Aktif” award in 2017, he hopes that he will encourage his younger siblings, as well as Brunei's youth, to become agri-preneur. In accordance with the vision of the nation or best known as Wawasan 2035 (Musa et al 2020).

3. Problem Statement

Syarikat Al Rasyid has been in service since 2016 and thus there will be problems facing the organization during the operation. One of the problems they face is money issues as the government only provided land to the paddy farmer. But also, Rasyid was fortunate enough to have financial support from his relatives. As well as a capital of \$15000 from LiveWIRE to help him kick off the paddy farm company. Another concern is that, regarding the land suitability as the given land is no previous examination to assess if the land is suitable for paddy cultivation. Therefore, it is also important for Rasyid to work long hours for this and, additionally, to work manually because the land is too damp and not ideal for vehicles and machinery to travel through. And lastly, due to the lack of infrastructure for paddy farming, especially irrigation issues as the current one is unreliable and not enough, because all farmers need to share clean water with each other. Most of them, therefore, rely on rainwater. However, the irrigation system provided in Wasan needs to be strengthened. Also, the sewage system, as well as poorly built roads, made it difficult to access the field. In the future, Rasyid raised the issue of infrastructure for paddy farming, especially in terms of land suitability and irrigation problems, which need to be resolved. Not to mention, he chose to inspire Brunei 's youth because of Brunei's heavy reliance on migrant labor (Musa et al 2020).

4. Case Analysis

4.1 The Warwick Model

The Warwick Model was developed at Warwick University by two academics, Chris Hendry and Andrew M. Pettigrew, in the early 1990s. Emphasizes the analytical approach to human resource management (HRM). It also acknowledges the effect of the role of staff functions on the content of the human resource plan. It is the continuation of the Harvard Model, consisting of an inner and outer relation, and puts more emphasis on strategy (Caker et al, 2003). Similarly, to the Harvard model, the Warwick Model's plan relies on five elements - Inner context, Outer context, Business Strategy context, Human Resource Management (HRM) context and lastly, HRM content. Approach material is defined as a hard HRM, it is generally accepted to put no focus on the needs of employees and thus, under its paradigm, any decision on the efficacy of HRM must be focused on market success criteria (Guest, 1999). It takes into account the importance of organizational learning in the strategy and thus integrates Hendry's paradigm of evolving strategy development rather than a solely top-down rationally designed solution.

Every element in the Warwick Model has its own component. The Inner context includes Culture, Structure, Politics or Leadership, Task-Technology and Business outputs. While the Outer context includes Socio-Economic, Technical, Political-Legal and Competitive. Also, the Business Strategy context includes Objectives, Product Market and Strategy & Tactics. HRM context includes Role, Definition, Organization and HR Outputs and lastly for the HRM content includes HR Flows, Work Systems, Reward Systems and Employee Relations.

4.2 Strengths

This model recognizes the corporate philosophy and activities of HR; it demonstrates the alignment of internal information and external content with the operational strategy. As such, the model has relevance for recruiting and selection, because internal and external material can be integrated with the organizational strategy. The strength of the model is that it recognizes and classifies major environmental effects on HRM. It maps the relations between the external and

the internal context, and discusses how HRM adapts to shifts in the context. The implication is that these organizations are achieving alignment. Another, in particular, impacts and shapes HR activities. It also charts the linkages between the climate and the organizational approach. In addition, this model discusses how HR can respond to changes in the external world.

4.3 Weaknesses

The drawback in the use of the Warwick model is that internal HR activities are not related to company production and thus efficiency. Furthermore, the introduction of a modern strategy in the business can be rather anarchic, since the need to understand and to specialist this approach can be time consuming for newcomers. Also, external impact factors defined by the Warwick Model, which can be divided into six broad factors. Themes: political; economic; social; technological; environmental; and legal concerns have an impact on the implementation of HRM policies in major construction firms. However, more analysis is recommended to verify the results stated as well as to broaden the reach of the case investigation to different industrial sectors.

5. Alternative Solutions

This section of the report paper would explore how the Warwick Model can be used to solve the challenges Syarikat Al Rasyid faces. As described above, the Warwick Model has the power to understand the organizational philosophy and practices of HR. This can then be seen in two phases: the economics of the country; and the economic state of the business. The national economy would show how much the government allocates to infrastructure growth, as well as general economic comfort and mechanisms that will allow private clients to invest in infrastructure. This, to add, would contribute to a large degree to the development of the industry and provide them with flexibility, and the opportunity to retain their workers, resulting in job protection for employees, and can also make long-term plans and policies.

The economic state of the business can be seen as the supply of the company. Resources: money, supplies, manpower, plant and machinery to be able to carry out programs. Availability of the services they said would prevent breaks in the execution of the project, and would guarantee that they finish the work on time and do not have to move their workers to disrupt their sense of security. The availability of capital, as noted by the respondents, would continue to provide workers with such contingencies and financial incentives. This will also help to fulfill the growth and advancement needs of workers that will see the development of the company in the long term.

The content in the Outer context is Socio-Economic. This can be based on the Cultural Motivation. Abdul Rasyid mentions that he considers his enterprise to be a reference to the titah of the Sultan, who constantly stressed the importance of agriculture in the construction of the nation and its future (Musa et al 2020). In other words, as an act of symbolic encouragement to His Highness the Sultan. Also, there is a mindset in Brunei where the quality of work is very poor, we only want foreign workers to come and do manual labor for us because it is cheaper. This is largely attributed to the overcrowding impact of cheap migrant labor, which can easily be accomplished and resulting in old agricultural practices, combined with aged producers, producing a sector that appears conventional and unattractive to young people. Then hence, the use of migrant labor that is readily available is also more affordable than the use of machines.

It can thus be concluded that the optimistic overpowering of the negative and hence the suggestion will be to adopt the Warwick model in Syarikat Al Rasyid in order to boost the company's long-term growth. One of the recommendations is under Business Strategy content. Exploring the Entrepreneurial Motives and Obstacles of Agripreneurs in Brunei Darussalam Market Potential and Visibility through Social Media As there is a lack of exposure of agripreneurs and their agribusinesses in Brunei and not many are aware of their presence, it is time to optimize the use of social media to support agriculture. The lack of publicity has given rise to traditional perceptions that farming is unprofitable and unpopular. Social media identified as one of the most important factors in the modern market environment and businesses must ensure that they are able to highlight the demands of the global business environment and react accordingly to developments. Also, the use of Social Media as a forum to build support and

publicize further educational programs. As a means to introduce the public and the institutions to their programs in order to inform them of the advantages of entering the programmes.

Hence, Social Media can be used as a platform to inspire the local youth in changing the negative mindset about agriculture. Like many other countries in the world, it is failing to draw and persuade its youth to participate in agriculture, and Brunei must see agriculture as a business opportunity (Rasidah Hj Abu Bakar, 2016). Thus, through experiences via social media, to understand what agriculture is, and to hear from encouraging or effective agri-farmers, this would slowly begin to convince young people and make them understand about agriculture, and later to see it as a business opportunity.

The use of mentoring in Syarikat Al Rasyid is a brilliant idea since in Brunei, there is a shortage of exposure to agriculture in schools. It is therefore necessary for there to be some sort of agricultural component from an early start. In order for more students to be involved in agribusiness, alternative education programs, such as the Family Farm School (FFS) model for young children in the Philippines, must be adopted at the basic education level. This is to help the graduates to generate income from selling crops while waiting for higher education administrative results.

6. Recommendations

Recommendation to solve challenges Syarikat Al rasyid face in terms of financial is to have Intrinsic Motivation which is family support. It is important for families to provide a strong support system even though some families do not have any knowledge or background of agriculture, besides family support can be used for their source of motivation. Also, families can also support financially due to some banks declined to lend money for start-up capital due to the risky nature of agricultural development associated with unforeseen weather patterns, floods and droughts, pests and certain harvests that could take time. In addition, young agri-preneurs are regarded as risky and their market strategies are also not deemed to be substantial. Unlike Abdul

Rasyid, his parents support him financially as he does not have trouble in terms of finding money to cover all other costs.

As a matter of fact, Brunei needs to allow money lending for start-up business just like in Malaysia. The AgroBank of Malaysia, for over 40 years of practice in agricultural banking can be considered a leading bank with an emphasis on the agricultural sector. Paddy-i Financing, or formerly known as Paddy Loan Scheme, is an award-winning revolutionary financing from Agrobank to satisfy the seasonal needs of paddy farmers and is ideal for planting and replanting paddy. Under this scheme, farmers are eligible to secure funding of up to RM2,500 per hectare or a maximum of RM50,000 to meet the criteria for the procurement of paddy, crops, fertilisers, land planning and other production costs associated with paddy farming. The scheme also offers a low profit rate subject to a profit rate of 3.25 per cent per harvest season and no collateral or guarantee needed for the funding. The features and incentives of the schemes have greatly enabled paddy farmers in particular to increase production output and profits.

In terms of irrigation system and drainage. The use of machinery and advanced technologies in agriculture in Brunei is also lagging behind other countries. There is an issue with the lack of up-to - date technologies in Brunei. In order to achieve food security in circumstances of low land supply, the Minister of Industry and Primary Resources announced that Brunei would rely more on "technology and know-how" using a higher variety of crops and more efficient farming techniques than on clearing agricultural forests (Maierbrugger, 2014). Theoretically, technology-substitution occurs as labor costs increase in comparison to capital costs as incomes rise in a growing economy, causing a change from labour-intensive to capital-intensive manufacturing methods (Webster, 1993).

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7. References

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